

DIAGNOSTICS OF MARKETING CONCEPTS OF COMMERCIAL BANKS IN PROVIDING LOANS TO AGRICULTURAL SECTOR OF KOSOVO

Petar Borisov¹, Fidan Qerimi, Arberesha Behluli

¹E-mail: peterborisov@gmail.com

Abstract

The purpose of this study is to analyze the key factors in marketing concepts applied by commercial banks in servicing its market segment "Loans and leasing for agribusiness" in Kosovo.

Through analysis aims at identifying the critical factors that banks incorporated within the selected marketing concept and how these factors influence the market presence of commercial banks in the research market segment. The research involves 10 leading commercial banks in the banking sector of Kosovo. In these economic structures are analyzed the following success factors for marketing concept: systematic application of marketing activities within the selected marketing concept; leadership in implementing the marketing concept; budgeting marketing concept. The main methods of collecting information necessary for the purposes of the questionnaire survey method and in-depth interview. Another important source of information audit reports of commercial banks. The commercial banks need to invest more in online advertising and the creation of products that successfully compete looming "threat" from new players. This means investing in the creation of the marketing information systems, the construction of "big data" sets and using innovative Internet solutions to create and implement marketing concepts offering products at minimal cost to the customer.

Key words: marketing concept, marketing strategy, commercial banks, market share, loans

Abstrakt

Ziel dieser Studie ist es, die Schlüsselfaktoren der Marketingkonzepte zu analysieren, die von den Geschäftsbanken bei der Bedienung ihres Marktsegments "Kredite und Leasing für das Agrargeschäft" im Kosovo angewandt werden.

Durch die Analyse sollen die kritischen Faktoren identifiziert werden, die die Banken in das ausgewählte Marketingkonzept einbeziehen, und wie diese Faktoren die Marktpräsenz der Geschäftsbanken im Forschungsmarktsegment beeinflussen. An der Untersuchung sind 10 führende Geschäftsbanken im Bankensektor des Kosovo beteiligt. In diesen Wirtschaftsstrukturen werden folgende Erfolgsfaktoren für das Marketingkonzept analysiert: systematische Anwendung von Marketingaktivitäten innerhalb des gewählten Marketingkonzepts; Führung bei der Umsetzung des Marketingkonzepts; Budgetierung des Marketingkonzepts. Die wichtigsten Methoden zur Erhebung von Informationen, die für die Zwecke der Methode der Fragebogenerhebung und des Tiefeninterviews erforderlich sind. Eine weitere wichtige Quelle für Informationsauditberichte von Geschäftsbanken. Die Geschäftsbanken müssen mehr in die Online-Werbung und die Schaffung von Produkten investieren, die erfolgreich mit der von neuen Akteuren drohenden "Bedrohung" konkurrieren. Dies bedeutet, dass sie in die Schaffung der

Marketing-Informationssysteme, den Aufbau "großer Datenmengen" und die Nutzung innovativer Internetlösungen investieren müssen, um Marketingkonzepte zu erstellen und umzusetzen, die dem Kunden Produkte zu minimalen Kosten anbieten.

Schlüsselwörter: Marketingkonzept, Marketingstrategie, Geschäftsbanken, Marktanteil, Kredite

Résumé

L'objectif de cette étude est d'analyser les facteurs clés des concepts de marketing appliqués par les banques commerciales pour desservir son segment de marché "Prêts et leasing pour l'agroalimentaire" au Kosovo.

L'analyse vise à identifier les facteurs critiques que les banques ont incorporés dans le concept de marketing sélectionné et comment ces facteurs influencent la présence des banques commerciales dans le segment de marché de la recherche. La recherche implique 10 banques commerciales de premier plan dans le secteur bancaire du Kosovo. Dans ces structures économiques sont analysés les facteurs de succès suivants pour le concept de marketing: application systématique des activités de marketing dans le cadre du concept de marketing sélectionné; leadership dans la mise en œuvre du concept de marketing; budgétisation du concept de marketing. Les principales méthodes de collecte des informations nécessaires aux fins de la méthode d'enquête par questionnaire et de l'entretien approfondi. Une autre source importante d'informations: les rapports d'audit des banques commerciales. Les banques commerciales doivent investir davantage dans la publicité en ligne et dans la création de produits capables de faire face avec succès à la "menace" que représentent les nouveaux acteurs. Cela signifie qu'elles doivent investir dans la création de systèmes d'information marketing, dans la construction de "grands ensembles de données" et dans l'utilisation de solutions Internet innovantes pour créer et mettre en œuvre des concepts marketing offrant des produits à un coût minimal pour le client.

Mots clés: concept de marketing, stratégie de marketing, banques commerciales, part de marché, prêts

Introduction

Modern banking with timid steps went into the transformation process necessary due to the rapid pace of innovation in the sector. Classical approach to banking has increasingly smaller role when it comes to achieving better market positions in a business environment characterized by increasing the presence of innovation and new market requirements. The processes of transformation in the financial sector led to significant changes in business orientation and marketing management of commercial banks, which relate to: (1)Adoption of marketing approach in the management of the bank as a leading; (2) Securitization of banking services; (3) the imposition of electronic banking and insurance and (4) monitoring of granted credit resources; (5) creating and managing big data (Bajrami, Hajdari and Qerimi, 2018). These changes pose significant challenges in the management and operation of commercial banks, which are expressed in that they have competence in the fields of marketing management, Internet security and encryption of data on construction and management of information systems (Gupta, 2011).

The modern market of banking services is saturated with a large presence of players - traditional and new, which determines the existence of fierce competition. "Traditional players" are banks that have

built a network of offices, departments and offices, where staff works to offer quality services at competitive conditions. "Traditional players" have a real infrastructure that creates tangible costs of bidding for banking services. "New players" are so-called "fintech" companies, unlike banks have a virtual infrastructure that enables them to significantly less cost price to compete with banks bidding for banking services. "New players" are highly innovative in the use of marketing principles to build competitive advantage (Romanova and Kudinska, 2017). They actively set up their marketing concepts using social networks and "B2B" partnerships. Under these conditions, the use of innovative elements in the marketing concept has a decisive role in the occupation of market positions. Therefore the analysis of marketing concepts has contemporary relevance in studying the market presence of the commercial bank. As a result of this analysis can identify the basic elements of the marketing concept that lead to market success.

The marketing concept of management is expressed in constant search for the best balance between user requirements, on the one hand, and the desire of commercial banks to get a higher profit on the other (Pride, 1994). It is a way of thinking - a management philosophy for overall activities of commercial banks (commercial banks). This philosophy influences the overall activities of the bank, not just on marketing activities (Hadzic, 2007). The main advantage of marketing management is to focus attention on the processes of the positions in the market in order to best comply with its requirements (Radev and Dirimanova, 2017) . Such deliberate coordination and coordinating business activities on surrounding businesses can increase efficiency. To succeed in a commercial bank, its managers must know these external forces to cover the relationships between them and understand what their real and potential impact on the organization (Radev, 2014). Above all, managers must manage commercial banks, so as to minimize the negative impact from the impact of external factors and maximize their positive impact on the organization.

A number of studies have been made on identifying the most important factors that you should know in developing the marketing concept of business organization. One of the researchers are of the opinion that marketing concept must be consistent with the organizational and management structure. (Walczak, 2005); (Zheng, 2010). Commercial banks have international structures and the principle of internationality management is directly advocated the formation of the organizational structure. That is why the formation of the marketing concept, commercial banks reported this principle. The kind of organizational and management structure is determined whether marketing unit will play a leading role. If the marketing department has a central role, he is able to apply systematic marketing activities within the selected management concept. Another critical factor that has an impact on the way of application is the marketing concept is the kind of leadership that is necessary in the marketing management of commercial banks (Bencheva and Stoeva, 2019). Leadership as a factor in the marketing environment has an impact not only in the choice of concept, but also in the control system implemented marketing activities.

Another important factor in the selection and application of the marketing concept of the commercial bank is its funding. Each management concept without funding is just one good wishes for market presence (Gronroos, 1991). Establishment of the budget of the marketing concept is one of the most important tasks in marketing planning (Hawkins, 2010). In size and structure of this budget shows

how commercial banks will address their offer to consumers of banking services and how it intends to ensure a sustainable market presence.

The purpose of this study is to analyze the key factors in marketing concepts applied by commercial banks in servicing its market segment "Loans and leasing for agribusiness" in Kosovo.

Through analysis aims at identifying the critical factors that banks incorporated within the selected marketing concept and how these factors influence the market presence of commercial banks in the research market segment.

The research involves 10 leading commercial banks in the banking sector of Kosovo. In these economic structures are analyzed the following success factors for marketing concept:

- Systematic application of marketing activities within the selected marketing concept;
- Leadership in implementing the marketing concept;
- Budgeting marketing concept.

The main methods of collecting information necessary for the purposes of the questionnaire survey method and in-depth interview. Another important source of information audit reports of commercial banks.

Limitations with which it is necessary to comply with this study are the following: (1) not every commercial bank perceives marketing approach to leading in their management, so those surveyed structures, marketing management be combined with other management actions ie marketing manager has other management functions. As part of the study marketing experts have no leader, and are under the rule to the managers of another department; (2) marketing budgets are not drawn according to the specifics of each individual market segment. This leads to uncertain about the effect of the budget on sales of services to agribusiness.

Each marketing concept is perceived as a tool to achieve more noticeable market presence. Therefore, the study analyzes the market presence of commercial banks in the market segment as a function of the chosen marketing concept. The study period is 2015-2017

Results

Characteristics of the surveyed sites. Table 1 show an origin of banks in respect of the location of the company "mother". The origin of the commercial banks in Kosovo is dominated by foreign countries, assets and personnel management. This foreign capital has a different origin (Germany, Austria, Turkey and Slovenia) and has great influence within the banking system. The main foreign capital comes from economically stable countries that share the very financial and market risk in the market of banking services in Kosovo. The share of domestic capital is very small and does not affect the activities of local banks. This defines the strong dependence of local banks regarding the financial position of the bank "mother" in terms of applied marketing concept for lending to agricultural businesses.

Table 1. Origin of the commercial bank. Source: Survey among 10 banks, 2017

	%
Kosovo	43
Germany	15
Turkey	14
Austria	14
Slovenia	14

Figure 1 provides information on owned assets and equity of the surveyed banks. Clearly outline the three banks that dominate in terms of disposable assets and equity. These are banks Raiffeisen Bank (RFB) with assets amounting to 5210 thousand euro and equity – 4080 thousand euro; ProCredit Bank (PB) of assets respectively 2530 thousand euro and equity - 1520 thousand euro and ISBANK with assets 2,540 thousand euro and equity - 1890 thousand euro. These three banks concentrate 59% of assets in the study group of commercial banks and 62% of the equity.

Figure 1. Assets and equity of the surveyed banks. Source: Audit reports.

Figure 2 is a credit resource that surveyed banks manage in the "Total loans". The largest contribution in lending are RFB, PB and ISBANK. These three banks possess 67% of credit resources market. Most often preferred for deposit are determined same three banks, as they possess 69% of the total cash deposits in the studied group of commercial banks.

Figure 2. Loans and deposits in surveyed banks. Source: Audit reports.

From the graphical analysis, it is clear that the bank services market is dominated by banks whose origin is local - 48% of all surveyed banks originate from Kosovo. The bank services market is dominated by three banks, which determines its monopolistic structure in terms of lending to businesses, and in terms of deposit of funds by citizens and businesses.

Agriculture is a risky sector and commercial banks in Kosovo for many years avoided its active lending. During the survey found that agribusiness in recent years, thanks to government support becomes more attractive sector lending by commercial banks. On figura 5 contains information on the activity of banks to lend to agriculture in Kosovo. The main measure used in the comparative analysis of bank lending is % of the total loan resource that they are granted the sector "agribusiness". It is clear that two strong banks dominate lending to agribusiness, namely are: first is RFB, which provided 25.3% of total credits awarded for development of the sector and the second is PB, whose share 20.6% of total given loans. ISBANK and Economic Bank stand out and it pretty poorly amid PB and RFB as active in terms of given loans for agribusiness in Kosovo. ISBANK has extended credit financing for agribusiness in Kosovo amounted to 5.1% of total distributed such and Economic Bank respectively - 4.2%. The remaining six banks have too symbolic contribution to agribusiness lending to Kosovo.

Figure 3. Lending to agribusiness in Kosovo. Source: Data from the commercial banks and own calculations.

It can be concluded that commercial banks still avoid actively lend to the agricultural business. They are seeking to diversify its range of credit, preferring to lend to other more attractive sectors. RFB and PB are the two commercial banks that see potential for growth in the segment "loans for agribusiness." They focus a significant portion of its credit resources to serve this market segment. The main reasons for this are: (1) most entrepreneurs in the sector receive their grants in accounts held by the two banks; (2) those entrepreneurs prefer to use credit services to these banks because of already built respect to service and the high costs of switching to the use of financial services.

Analysis of the implementation of marketing concepts. Marketing concepts applied to commercial banks in research market segment is analyzed and evaluated in terms of their level of performance. Marketing concept to commercial banks is seen as being consistent implementation of a series of interconnected and self-differentiated marketing activities.

Through a specially developed questionnaire monitored the degree of implementation of marketing activities of commercial banks set by their chosen marketing concept. Figure 9 provides information on the extent of implementation of marketing activities in the studied group of commercial banks.

Marketing concept of the bank includes the steps - analysis, planning, execution and control. By specified 15 questions seek to determine the extent of implementation of the activities of each stage of the application of the marketing concept in the research market segment.

On the first question, "Is there a built marketing information system (MIS)?" 50% of those surveyed marketing professionals working in commercial banks have given a positive response, 30% of respondents said that they have such a system, but it is not autonomous and building block of a higher management systems (see figure 4).

To the question "Do you analysis the external environment," 80% of marketing managers say they do this kind of analysis and believe it is useful in developing the marketing concept of commercial banks. Only 10% of the total respondents, declare that they make a partial analysis of the external environment, as the main reason for this, they argue that unseen need this kind of analysis.

The next question in the survey was "well defined is the mission of your bank?". Here 100% of respondents give a positive response and believe that the mission is an important tool for effective marketing planning.

To the question "Your employees familiar you are with the organization's mission and share it?", 80% of marketing managers said "Yes". These results give reason to believe that the mission was used as the primary motivator in the implementation of the marketing concept of the bank. Only 3 percent of marketing managers said "No".

When asked "Do you segment your market?", 60% of marketing managers said "Yes"; 30% said they partially do this activity and 10% in general do not carry this out.

The question "Is developed profile of each target segment?", 50% of respondents gave a positive answer, 40% gave the answer "Partly" and 10% said "No".

An important point in correct positioning of the financial product is the choice of appropriate marketing mix. With the question "Has a specific marketing mix for each target segment?" we seek to establish whether, in practice, commercial banks give this matter in imposing its marketing concept. Of all respondents (marketing managers), 50% give a positive response, 30% said that this activity is made partly and 20% gave a negative answer "No". The results of this response indicates that the preparation of specific marketing mix in the research market segment is not implemented systematically. Reasons for this could be sought that the majority of commercial banks believe that it is worth doing so, adopting the philosophy of mass marketing ie

The question "Does the marketing objectives are quantified?", 90% of respondents said "Yes" and 10% gave a negative answer, "No". Quantification of marketing objectives is an important principle in marketing planning. This is because marketing objectives are used as standards for control over the marketing concept of commercial banks. The high performance of this marketing activity proves that marketing managers also share this principle in their work.

Marketing plan is one of the important tools for planning and control of the marketing concept to commercial banks. To the question "Have you developed a marketing plan?", 50% of surveyed marketing

managers respond "yes", 20% gave the answer "Partly" and 30% gave the answer "No". The results of the survey suggest that the development of a marketing plan as part of the marketing concept is not implemented in full. Reasons for this are: (1) managers believe that targeting a market segment marketing plan will help them particularly; (2) market segment is not as attractive and do not deserve wasting resources for making a marketing plan; (3) the bank "mother" is responsible for developing this type of plan in challenging market segment.

The question "Is there a clearly defined marketing strategy to achieve the objectives?", 90% of marketing managers said that their bank has got a marketing strategy, 10% state that they have got, but it is not complete. The results show that marketing managers are concerned about the performance of the marketing strategy and define it as one of the most important in the planning of the marketing concept to commercial banks.

The existence of a reasonable marketing strategy is not sufficient conditions to achieve efficiency in implementing the marketing concept. This strategy should relies on a specific competitive advantage - 60% of marketing managers declare that their bank it happens, 20% say it happens in their bank partly and 20% said that this strategy is not oriented in that way. The results of this question shows that achieving competitive advantage in the market segment "Loans and leasing for agribusiness" is performed by a specific marketing strategy.

The consistency of the marketing strategy with other business strategies of commercial banks is another critical factor that depends on the effectiveness of the marketing concept. On this question, only 40% of respondents gave a positive answer. These results suggest that marketing managers do not make sense in the coordination of marketing activities of commercial banks with other business activities.

Formulation of marketing strategy is not sufficient conditions to increase the efficiency of applied marketing approach to management of commercial banks. Each strategy adopted as an official document of strategic management without obtaining the necessary financing remains only "wishful thinking." To the question "Are there sufficient financial resources to carry out the chosen marketing strategy?", 70% of respondents gave a positive response, which means that this activity is important and is accomplished in the majority of the surveyed banks.

The question "Is it clear who is responsible for what in implementing the strategy?", 60% of respondents said "yes", 30% said "partly" and 10% say it is not clear. The results indicate that staff in most of the cases is aware of the implementation of marketing strategy.

The last question in the survey is "Is there a system for monitoring the implementation of selected marketing strategy?". On this question only 50% said "Yes". This result shows that at this stage the bankers are not motivated essential to implement a controlling system.

The analysis can be concluded that most significant activities for banks to carry out are the following: (1) a clear definition of the marketing strategy; (2) a clear definition of the mission; (3) an analysis of the external environment. The results of the survey show that commercial banks in the development of the segment "Loans and leasing for agribusiness" rely on effective goal setting and quality in its marketing. Almost all surveyed banks invest in analysis and goal setting. The most neglected marketing activities are: (1) coordination of marketing strategy with other business strategies of the bank; (2) establishment of a system for monitoring the implementation of the marketing strategy; (3) the

development of specific marketing mix positioning of the credit services in market segment; (4) developing a marketing plan.

Figure 4. Level of implementation of marketing activities among commercial banks. Source: Survey among 30 marketing managers working in the surveyed banks.

Formulation, selection, implementation and control of the marketing concept of the commercial bank is a continuous process and its interruption by systemic deficiencies in the ongoing marketing activities lead to lower efficiency of marketing management and loss of market power in the market. Therefore, identification of gaps in the implementation of marketing concepts to commercial banks is an important element of the analysis and evaluation of the effectiveness of the applied marketing concept to commercial banks.

Analysis of the lead in the application of marketing concepts. Effectiveness of marketing activities are largely determined by the style of leadership that is required for marketing management of commercial banks. In this part of the study is analyzed the leadership of marketing managers that they impose within the selected marketing concept of commercial banks. The philosophy that managers profess the organization of marketing activities determined the outcome of activity-layered. Every manager imposes his own style of leadership, which is very specific and is determined by the situation

(the situation of decision-making process) as well as experience, knowledge and competencies to deal with the typical problems surrounding the organization of marketing activities.

Leadership of marketing managers examine and evaluate on the basis of specially designed questions in the questionnaire. Figure 5 presents information on the preferences of marketing managers to the particular type of leadership, which seek to impose commercial banks. The results suggest that marketing managers prefer to respect the principle of undivided authority in organizing marketing activities, 33.3% of respondents chose the answer "Centralized type of leadership." Another preferred style of leadership among managers is the "bureaucratic-type" that is characterized by the fact that it is easy to implement control and traceability of implemented marketing activities. Commercial banks as specific business structure are required to operate with the principles of transparency, relevance and responsiveness to market changes. Therefore the use of "centralized type of" leadership and "bureaucratic type of" leadership are preferred by marketing managers among surveyed commercial banks. These types of leadership have the following weaknesses: (1) high requirements on the manager, he must be an experienced administrator and he has willing to lose a large part of his working time for paper work; (2) do not share the risk in marketing management with the rest of the company staff; (3) lost to feedback from staff. Key strengths of these types of leadership are: (1) quick decisions, leading to increased proactivity to the surrounding environment; (2) avoids conflicts; (3) easily monitor the implemented marketing activities in commercial banks. (1) high demands on the manager, he must be an experienced administrator and is willing to lose a large part of their working time accounts; (2) do not share the risk in marketing management with the rest of the staff; (3) lost to feedback from staff. Key strengths of these types of leadership are: (1) quick decisions, leading to increased proactivity to the surrounding environment; (2) avoids conflicts; (3) easily monitor the implemented marketing activities in commercial banks.

Figure 5. Preferences marketing managers to leadership in marketing. Source: Results of a survey among 30 managers, working in the surveyed banks.

Figure 6. Approaches to motivate the staff to implement the marketing activities. Source: Results of a survey among 30 managers working in the surveyed banks.

Each style of leadership is required and determined by the view of manager for success and his attitude for the future development of the organization in which he operates. Figure 7a shows the results of answers to the question included in the survey - "What are your future expectations for your presence in the market" Lending to agribusiness "?.

Figure 7a. Managers' expectations regarding market presence of their commercial bank in research segment. Source: Results of a survey among 30 managers working in the surveyed banks.

More than 1/3 of respondents said that they are optimistic about the market presence of their bank in the segment "Loans and leasing of agribusiness." Equally of surveyed managers said that their bank will maintain its market position within the applied marketing concept. The results showed that the attitude of managers' success in the market is essential in the surveyed banks. In other words, there is a tangible sense of stability and potential for market success in 2/3 of surveyed marketing managers.

Expression of the chosen style of leadership is the applied marketing strategy of the manager in commercial banks. Leadership directly affects the process of formulating a marketing strategy. In the choice of marketignova strategy that makes the manager can understand what business concept to follow it and what management principles seek to manifest in their work.

Figure 7b. contains information on the preferences of marketing executives on strategy for marketing management in commercial banks.

Figure 7b. Preferences of managers to the types of marketing strategies. Source: Results of a survey among 30 managers working in the surveyed banks.

i Marketing managers said they follow a strategy of imitation positioning of banking products in the research market segment - 33.3% recognize the strategy of imitation, as a useful tool for imposing on the market. Only 20.3% of managers rely on the strategy of exclusivity positioning of products in the market segment. It can be concluded that marketing managers strive to be innovative in terms of applied marketing concept as quality of service and give a sense of satisfaction of client in their consumption.

Another important element of the marketing leadership is how to define the target market. Proper profiling the client type is critical element in effectiveness of imposing style of leadership on the applied marketing activities. Market segmentation is one of the most important activities in product positioning in the market. Figure 8 provides information on the criteria that marketing managers use in the formulation of the target market. It is clear that the main criteria is profiling the income of potential borrower, 95% of managers indicate that criteria. Another important criterion is "age", 90% of managers use this segmentation criterion in shaping the market. Another important criteria for segmentation is the location of the borrower - 83% of managers use it in their marketing concept.

Figure 8. Criteria for market segmentation used by managers. Source: Results of a survey among 30 managers working in the surveyed banks.

Analysis of marketing budgets. Achieving the effects of the applied marketing concept depends on the budget, which must comply and running marketing manager at commercial banks. Still there is no

single formula by which to determine the optimal structure of the marketing budget to ensure high levels of sales.

Figure 9 provides information on the amount of marketing costs, which commercial banks make to enforce its product in the market segment. The biggest marketing budgets are developed by the leaders in the market segment - RFB and PB. RFB finance its marketing concept with 805 thousand euro and PB with 512 thousand euro. VKT also makes significant marketing costs compared to other commercial banks, the amount of marketing budget is nearly 500 thousand euro. The smallest marketing budget stands in Ziraat Bank with 105 thousand euro.

The structuring of the marketing budget is subject to the principle of achieving higher sales in the market segment. Choosing a structure of this type of budget determines what kind of communication mix will be used to get the message of a commercial bank to its customers (current and future). Figure 9 is a comparative characteristic of the budget structure for the marketing of commercial banks. It is clear that the leaders in the market segment RFB and PB rely on radio and television network as channels of communication with its customers.

Figure 9. Marketing costs of commercial banks. Source: Own data.

RFB allocates 55% of the cost of radio and television advertising and PB - 80%. PB managed to improve its market position thanks to better structuring their marketing budget. The results of the comparative analysis of the marketing budgets of commercial banks shows that in the structure of the budget dominate (1) the cost of radio and television advertising and (2) the cost of Internet advertising (see figure 10). These are the two largest items in the budget, which indicates that commercial banks rely on television media as the main channel of communication with its customers. Cost of visualization (cost of billboards, brochures, posters and promotional materials) have the lowest percentage in the structure of the marketing budget (their share varies from 4% to 10% in the analyzed budgets of banks).

Figure 10. Structure of the marketing budgets of commercial banks. Source: Data from the commercial banks and own calculations.

Market presence of commercial banks in segment "Lending to agribusiness". Market presence of banks in the segment "Lending to agribusiness" examine by the indicator - market share. Figure 6 gives comparative characteristic of commercial banks by achieved market share in the researched market segment. Clearly stand two player in the market segment - RFB and PB. RFB manage 32.5% of the market for loans to agribusiness, and PB - 24.3%. The data set in the graph indicate that both commercial banks have complete dominance in researched market segment. These are the most active banks in terms of offering financial services for agribusiness. Total two commercial banks possess 56.8% of the market, which means that every second customer prefers to use credit for its agribusiness granted by RFB or PB. Achieving this dominance in the market segment of these two commercial banks can be explained by the following factors: commercial banks actively diversifying its financial products to the farmers needs; provide the best conditions on lending market; taking care to maintain customer loyalty, resulting in better conditions for refinancing loans; sluggish presence of other commercial banks in the researched market segment. Achieved a market share of both commercial banks is an indicator of their market power. Dominance in the market segment of two players sharpen competition between them, which benefits customers – farmers (see figure 11). At this stage, managers from group of surveyed commercial banks, said that exhaustion of the segment is too small and therefore it is not actively attacking them.

Figure 12 shows dynamics of lending to the researched segment of commercial banks. Used method of single index to identify changes in credit expansion in the research market segment. The largest growth in lending segment is PB, which has increased concluded credit agreements with 10,1%. It RFB, which realizes growth in loans by 5.9%. A sizeable increase (+ 5.5%) of the signed credit contracts with farmers account and NLB Prishtina. The increase in sales of credit resources of these three commercial banks is not significant (ranging between 5% and 10%). According featured in Figure 12, RFB losing ground in the market segment against its main competitor PB. However, RFB remains the largest market share. Market power segment noticeably lose Komercijalna Banka ad Beograd (-50%).

Figure 11. Market share of commercial banks in segment "Loans and leasing of agribusiness". Source: Data from the commercial banks and own calculations.

Figure 12. Credit growth (%) in the segment "Loans and leasing for agribusiness"

Conclusions

In the market segment "Loans and leasing for agribusiness" dominate only two players - RFB and PB. These two commercial banks have a dominant influence on the market segment. These are the major commercial banks in passing on subsidy payments for farmers in Kosovo. Another factor for the hegemony of these banks in the segment is the concentration of financial capital in these structures, expressed in disposable assets and equity. More than half of credit resources is concentrated in these two banks, enabling them to benefit from economies of scale in lending to agribusiness in Kosovo. Potential market

segment is very limited and can "feed" two or three commercial banks that are in keen competition with each other. In developing research market segment, commercial banks showed a systematic approach in terms of analyzing the environment and goal setting. These are the two most significant marketing activities positioning of loan products in the market segment "Loans and leasing of agribusiness". There are systemic flaws of commercial banks in terms of implementation and control of selected marketing concept, service research market segment. The main reasons for this are: (1) lack of understanding of the seriousness of the problem by marketing managers (they believe that control of this stage is not important in their function) and (2) deformations of the systems to control and monitor the implementation of marketing concept. This deformations are determined by the fact that the system is constructed as part of higher management system of commercial banks, whose parameters are defined in advance by the bank "mother", which requires priority to collect information for the purpose of financial and investment control. In the implementation of the marketing concept, marketing managers primarily use the principle of undivided authority, which allows them to be flexible in a changing business environment. In the pursuit of efficiency of applied marketing concept, commercial banks rely heavily on the cost of TV, radio and Internet advertising. These are structurally costs in the marketing budgets of surveyed commercial banks. Implementing the selected marketing concepts is accomplished by settling for product differentiation. More than half of commercial banks follow this principle to achieve better market positions in the research market segment.

Price competition in the market for financial services is acute and will become increasingly fierce due to the advent of more "new players" offering innovative products to customers at minimal cost. These new players are financial institutions that provide banking services without investing in creating a real infrastructure of a network of bank branches and offices, not to engage in their activities huge number of staff. Such "new players" are "fintech" companies that offer mobile applications for the financial needs of costumers. These companies have a virtual infrastructure for customer service failed bid to compete with commercial banks at customer service while minimizing costs of operating activity. Their proposed fees and commissions are much lower than those of commercial banks as their product is accessible at any time and place, thanks to the fact that it is an integral part of the smartphone software. Other innovators who successfully compete with the commercial banks are those that offer services based on "peer to peer" system, which system allows significantly reduce the cost of carrying out banking transactions called "money transfer" and achieve leadership in the market segment. These two innovative models in the future will increasingly compete and push commercial banks, which do not take into account in their business models and marketing concepts latest market trends.

The commercial banks need to invest more in online advertising and the creation of products that successfully compete looming "threat" from new players. This means investing in the creation of the marketing information systems, the construction of "big data" sets and using innovative Internet solutions to create and implement marketing concepts offering products at minimal cost to the customer.

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